

Applying User Experience (UX) methodologies to science: the example of the BioSODA user interface

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Abstract

We applied user experience methodologies to the user interface of BioSODA, a new web service for intuitive research in the life sciences. While the scientific quality of the tool was not questioned in this work, nor its usefulness for the life sciences community, we focused on user experience through close collaboration between developers, users and UX experts.

This is the first part of a larger project that will go as far as the design of the new BioSODA user interface. It took place in January 2019, in the form of a one-day workshop whose aim was to brainstorm on the different types of BioSODA users.

The next steps will include user interviews to validate the findings of this work, as well as user testing sessions to make sure that the BioSODA prototype meets the users' needs and expectations.

Overall, this work showed that putting the user at the center of the development of user interfaces is not necessarily a time-consuming task, but rather a mindset shift.

1. Scientific context

Although data integration promises to be an important driver for extracting new knowledge from the wealth of publicly available biological data, the heterogeneity of the source data, both syntactically and semantically, makes this crucial task very difficult. Ontologies are currently widely used to allow data integration and exchanges in semantic data. However, even though many resources use ontologies, the aggregation and coherence of multiple information coming from different sources is still a complex, often manual, task.

To address this issue in the life science domain, the BioSODA project (Biological Search Over Database) (Sima, et al., 2019) proposes a solution by introducing an ontology-based federated approach for data integration, applied to three heterogeneous biological databases: Bgee (<https://bgee.org/>), OMA (<https://omabrowser.org/oma/home/>), and UniProtKB (www.uniprot.org).

These first-class databases are part of the portfolio of the SIB Swiss Institute for Bioinformatics (www.sib.swiss), which provides the national and international life sciences community with state-of-the-art bioinformatics databases, and software tools. Moreover, these databases span different and complementary areas of biological knowledge:

- Bgee enables to retrieve and compare gene expression patterns in multiple animal species,
- OMA focuses on the inference of orthologs among complete genomes,
- UniProtKB is a central hub for the collection of functional information on proteins.

The objective behind BioSODA is to convert intuitive search terms into complex search queries through novel Google-like search options, allowing researchers with no prior technical training to query databases intuitively and concentrate on scientific questions, in a similar way that we are used to doing today with a search engine. In other words, BioSODA makes running queries in huge quantities of bioinformatics data an easier task. The program also makes search suggestions in order to display information that has not been expressly sought. Unlike a search through simple web pages, searching through databases offers additional value by enabling the construction of a complete response based on the multiple fragments of data residing in the three sources.

Concretely, BioSODA's goal is to enable users to get answers from questions of type 'What are the human genes which have a known association to glioblastoma, and which furthermore have an orthologous gene expressed in the rat's brain?'. Indeed (Figure 1):

- Human proteins associated with glioblastoma can be obtained from UniProtKB
- The orthologs of these proteins in the rat can be obtained from OMA
- The genes expressed in the rat brain can be obtained from Bgee

The system should be able to process this question and provide a list of answers, perhaps also using some feedback from the user when it does not fully understand the question or serve as an "exploratory" tool for researchers starting to explore data from the databases and getting familiar with their contents.

BioSODA comes thus to help with questions of the type:

- Show me gene names / Show me all species / Show me all species names
- What are the anatomic entities where the ptgs1 gene is absent? / What are the anatomic entity names where the ptgs1 gene is absent? / What are the anatomic entity names where the ptgs1 gene is absent in homo sapiens? (or in Rattus?) /What are the anatomic entities and species where the ptgs1 gene is absent?
- What are the species names for the mt-co1 gene?

Figure 1: Example of use of BioSODA with the question of type “What are the human genes which have known association to glioblastoma and which furthermore have an orthologous gene expressed in the rat’s brain?”

2. The UX study

2.1. Why an UX study?

Life scientists and clinicians use increasingly complex and sophisticated software and databases to do their daily work. At the same time, the new generation of researchers -both technology experts and application-oriented consumers -is raising expectations in terms of ease of use of resources. Indeed, beyond the established reputation for scientific excellence, there is still much to be done to ensure that the scientific tools are used to their full potential while creating a positive experience for users by meeting user needs. UX study is the process by which users are identified, together with their needs and wishes, and are incorporated into product design to deliver greater user experiences (UX). Indeed, an early study of the user experience saves time and money in the long term: an efficient product design drastically reduces development times and reduces training needs as well as technical support to users, allowing them to focus on scientific and content developments. It is therefore crucial to understand who the users are and how the tool can be employed, in order to develop a product that fits user needs and that is used by the community.

2.2. How did we proceed for the UX Study?

At the time of the work, BioSODA had a template-based interface not yet public. The great challenge we faced was to design an interface that was both appealing and efficient for the scientific community, without having a starting point or comparison. We thus developed an ad-hoc UX process, using techniques issued from the marketing environment applied to this context, with critical thinking and considering the peculiarity of such an unconventional product.

We have run a 1-day moderated workshop with the four developers and two potential users, to have a global view of the product and to understand the interests of the stakeholders.

During this workshop, similar, but much shorter than a condensed *design sprint* (Knapp, Zeratsky, & Kowitz, 2016), we have analysed and developed the following points:

1. Identify user needs (30')
2. Depict proto-personas (30')
3. Build user journeys (60')
4. Identify pain points (30')
5. Draw product sketches (30')
6. Reach a consensus (90')

2.2.1. User needs

BioSODA is built to be addressed to the large scientific community. In order to design the product for the users, it is essential to understand the potential user needs that the product aims to meet.

The discussion within the group lead to the following consideration:

- What are the needs that the tool wants to meet?
 - Interconnect resources automatically
 - Ask scientific questions in “layman terms” and have an answer without understanding the technical information
 - Span multiple domains
 - Aggregation of results
 - Help biologists to work with genes in bioinformatics w/o knowing the databases
- How does it meet the needs?
 - It gives direct answers that are clear enough and straight to the point
 - It avoids unnecessary indications to databases or technical details of search
 - It clearly communicates to the user what is the answer that it is able to give

- How does it compare to competitors, if existing? Why is it going to be better?
 - Basic Google search: too many information, scientific quality cannot be assessed
 - When Google addresses the user to scientific databases: the user without deep knowledge of bioinformatics often finds those databases too complex
 - NCBI website: the information is spread in multiple datasets, also too complex for the layman.

2.2.2. Proto-personas

Personas are fictional characters, which are stand-ins for user types that are meant to use the tools, together with their needs and expectations. Creating personas helps the software developers recognise that different people have different needs and expectations, and thus create an optimal user experience for the end users.

Personas are abstractions or archetypes, fictitious models of users based on real data collected in the field. If the latter are missing, personas lose their usefulness. For a brand-new product such as BioSODA, as data on the user community are not yet available, creating personas is meaningless. While personas are not at hand, “proto-personas” come to help. Proto-personas respond to the problem of how to create characters when little data on users are available (Gothelf, 2012). They are variants of traditional personas, with the difference that initially they are not based on user searches. Conversely, they are derived from workshops with project stakeholders, who are stimulated to isolate characteristics and motivations of the target audience through their knowledge of the domain. The proto-personas provide a starting point for the evaluation of the products or services and create some design hypotheses. They are essential for the success of the product as they help to make stakeholders more aware of the importance of user research and a user-centred approach during the entire product development

Together with the stakeholders we brainstormed two types of proto-personas: (i) a beginner (Simon), who represents the typical biologist that would use the tool to get an answer to a scientific questions in “layman terms” and have an answer without needing to understand the technical information behind; and (ii) an expert (Olga), who represents the user familiar with programming and advanced interfaces, looking for an output to integrate in his/her script (Table 1).

	<p>DESCRIPTION & BEHAVIOUR</p> <p>(who is (s)he? what background does (s)he have? what does (s)he like? how does (s)he behave?)</p>
<p>NEEDS & GOAL</p> <p>(what is (s)he looking for? why does (s)he need the tool?)</p>	<p>FRUSTRATION</p> <p>(why can't (s)he use existing tools? what is missing? what doesn't (s)he like?)</p>

BEGINNER		EXPERT	
<p>Simon</p>	<p>DESCRIPTION & BEHAVIOUR</p> <p>Bioinformatician</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knows more about databases and software tool • Is an advanced user of search interfaces • Knows logical architecture of computer • Understands biology • Has good programming skills 		

NEEDS & GOAL	FRUSTRATION	NEEDS & GOAL	FRUSTRATION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Needs confirmation to validate his research or open a new topic Wants to answer his question Wants all the info available on that subject in one single page The output should be a text 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No idea on how to start, where to look for the answer He's overwhelmed by what he finds on the net 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Needs a quick and reliable answer Needs to integrate the answer in her script Wants to understand how the answer is built The output should be a script 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are too many tools to use, she needs a fast and direct answer

Table 1: Proto-personas. On the top, a schematic table for representation of the user. The four quadrants identify the who is the user, what is his/her scope and his/her feelings. Below, the two proto-personas: Simon, the beginner user and Olga the expert user.

2.2.3. User journeys

Once proto-personas are defined, it is necessary to understand how they (would) behave on the platform, what they are thinking and how they are feeling, and what are the possible challenges and opportunities to grab in order to make the platform useful and appreciated by all types of users. We thus created user journeys, simplified user maps that respond to the question “*how do people actually use the product?*” (Babich, 2019). In general, user journey tells the interaction between a user and a product, through a summary representation of all the phases of the experience and the description of all the actions (or activities) phase by phase.

	Simon - beginner Olga - advanced	Start	Use	Interpret
What does the user do?		<p>WANTS to understand how a certain search is performed</p> <p>WANTS to know more about a gene</p>	<p>Fill the example and test it</p> <p>Enter a query for which he doesn't know the answer</p> <p>Enter a query for which he knows the answer</p>	<p>Get the result</p> <p>Get the ID of the query</p> <p>Download as a TXT file</p>
What is the user thinking?		<p>I have no query...</p> <p>Which domains are covered?</p> <p>How do I enter my query?</p>	<p>Am I going to have something?</p> <p>Is it going to give a reliable answer?</p> <p>Am I going to get something?</p> <p>Will the query take long?</p> <p>Is the results table going to be big?</p>	<p>Do the results make sense with respect to my knowledge?</p> <p>Will the output be understandable?</p> <p>In which format can I download the result?</p> <p>Will I be able to download the result?</p>
How is the user feeling?				
What are the opportunities?		<p>Provide an example query</p> <p>1st time use: have some documentation. Info about what the tool can do</p> <p>Give suggestions on how to use the tool</p> <p>description on how to use the tool</p>	<p>Compress the results</p> <p>Output formats</p> <p>Indicate if search is running or if it is stuck</p> <p>Add waiting/process bar</p>	<p>Results need to be understandable by Simon ("human readable")</p> <p>Give suggestions/proposing search (more specific) in the results</p> <p>Advanced fields</p> <p>Predefined fields (basic info)</p> <p>Get the query, how it was built</p> <p>Save the query or bookmark it</p>

Figure 2: User journeys of the two proto-personas for the three phases, Start, Use and Interpret. In pink Simon, the beginner user; in yellow Olga, the expert user.

For BioSODA we have identified 3 phases: *Start (Onboarding)*, *Use* and *Interpret (Results/Output)*. Steps, feelings and opportunities are represented in Figure 2. It is worth to mention that the “opportunities” row shows insights gained from mapping; it tells how the user experience can be optimized and what are the important features to include in the prototype. For BioSODA, we have identified three main classes of opportunities: (i) at the onboarding level, to facilitate the first approach with the tool (e.g. with documentation, examples or an introductory video/description); (ii) at the usage level, to make the running process smoother and less obscure; and (iii) at the outcome level, in order to simplify the interpretation of the result and to generate an easy-to-use/reuse output (e.g. in the appropriate format).

2.2.4. Pain points and solutions

The user journeys for Simon and Olga helped us to uncover the major *pain points* and thus brainstorm *solutions*. A pain point is a specific problem that the user may be experiencing while interacting with the tool and that may cause the user to go away. Identification of pain points aims to minimise the friction in the user journeys: they represent the problems that have to be solved, through a consistent and effective solution, to improve the product. Our basic approach in the workshop was the following:

- Identify major pain points directly from the user journeys
- Translate them into goals for the team
- Draw solutions

Pain points stem directly from the “thinking” and “feeling” rows of the user journeys: whenever Simon and Olga doubt about the tool or wonder about its use or effectiveness, a pain point is identified. The aim of this phase is to find solutions that dispel their doubts and concerns and to create a pleasant user experience along the entire journey. Figure 3 shows the solutions to the major pain points during the three steps of the process (*Start, Use, Interpret*). It is interesting to note that most of the solutions correspond to the opportunities that have emerged during the analysis of the user journeys, but they are described in a more tangible way: they represent concrete solutions that are to be implemented directly in the product.

Figure 3: Solutions to the major pain points during the three steps of the process (*Start, Use and Interpret*).

2.2.5. Consensus sketch

Finally, we were able to draw sketches. Sketches focus on the ideation process: each participant draws with pen and paper his/her interpretation of the future concept on a blank canvas. This avoids empty brainstorming and brings interesting solutions on the table. We allocated 30 minutes to the participants to individually draw their idea of the perfect website and we then asked to share it to the other participants. In this phase, each team member presents his/her sketch to the group and discusses the various features of the concept. This phase is very interesting and should not be shortened: it provides an opportunity for the

team to gain a better understanding of the solutions and prioritize the various features. Together with the team, we finally drew a consensus sketch on a single idea through decision-making exercises (Figure 4A).

2.3. Wireframe and prototype

Figure 4: Sketches, consensus and wireframe. (A): (a) and (b) display individual sketches; (c), (d) and (e) show the consensus drawn on the board. In the wireframe (B), the three steps of the process are represented subsequently, Start, Use and Interpret.

The consensus sketch on the board led to the creation of a wireframe. A wireframe is a visual guide displaying the skeletal framework of a website. It shows the main layout or arrangement of the website's content, including interface elements and navigational systems, and how they interact together. It does not include graphics, special fonts, styles and colour, because the focus lies in functionality, behaviour, and main content. The main goal of this stage is organizing the product's content and flow in a way that allows users to achieve their goals within the product most easily. In other words, it focuses on what a product does, not what it looks like (Paul, 2019). In many cases, however, few graphics are included, in order to clearly illustrate to the user how the product or website would look, especially so as not to discourage him/her while evaluating the functionality. The wireframe was developed on AdobeXD. The relevant screens for the three steps of the user journeys are shown in Figure 4B.

The wireframe was then implemented in a first prototype, available only internally at the moment, Figure 5 displays a few screens of the tool under construction. Comparing Figure 5 to Figure 4B, it is evident how the wireframe helped the design of the interface.

Figure 5: First open prototype of BioSODA. Similarities with the wireframe are visible comparing to Figure 4B.

2.4. SUS (System Usability Scale)

To evaluate the success of the prototype, in particular compared to the initial interface, we assessed the usability at the two stages: before and after the UX study and implementation. The System Usability Scale (SUS, (Brooke, 1996)) is commonly employed to score the usability of a product or service. It consists in a

simple survey that provides a high-level score for the usability of a product. Comparing SUS scores across different stages of a project shows how usability is changing. The score is calculated using the answers to a ten-item questionnaire. Users answer the questions based on their experiences with the product. The score is a value between 0 and 100, with higher values indicating better usability.

The SUS ranks read as below:

- SUS > 79, (<85th pctl) excellent
- 68 < SUS < 79 good
- SUS = 68 (=50thpctl) average
- 51 < SUS < 68 poor
- SUS < 51 (<15thpctl) very bad

SUS was used to assess the usability of both the template-based interface (before) and the wireframe (after), by 4 users. An average SUS evaluated the website as “very bad” at first usage, while the wireframe was evaluated “good” by the same users (Table 2).

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	TOT
Before	1	4	3	4	3	4	2	4	2	2	32.5
	3	5	1	4	2	3	2	4	2	3	27.5
	5	2	5	4	3	1	2	5	4	4	57.5
	1	3	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	3	32.5
avg SUS before workshop											37.5
After	4	4	4	4	5	1	4	1	5	2	75
	5	1	5	2	5	1	4	5	5	2	82.5
	3	2	3	4	4	2	4	3	3	2	60
	4	1	3	1	3	1	5	1	3	3	77.5
avg SUS on the final wireframe											73.75

Table 2: SUS rating before and after. The first prototype received a rating of 37.5 (“very bad”) and the final wireframe received a rating of 73.75 (“good”).

It is important to note that SUS is widely employed for a quick analysis in UX studies, because of its simplicity of use. However, some glitches can be identified in using it for such a highly specific tool. In fact, it is not very representative of the behaviour of the user during the tests. Some questions are actually hard to

understand and often misinterpreted. As an example, at the question #10, “I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system”, users were answering not with respect to the usability of the system, but with respect to the scientific knowledge needed to use it. A tailor-made evaluation scale should be developed for such advanced tools and interfaces and this will be subject to careful analysis of a future study. It is worth mentioning that other usability scales exist for specific situations, for example, the SUPR-Q, or the WAMMI (Kirakowski, Claridge, & Whitehand, 1998) for the evaluation of websites.

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